

DIGITAL PRESERVATION OF HERITAGE FOR CRISIS PREVENTION, PEACEBUILDING, AND YOUTH EMPOWERMENT: INSIGHTS FROM OMBATSE CRISIS

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critical necessity for context-sensitive, participatory preservation frameworks that not only secure digital surrogates but foster cultural resilience and epistemic justice in societies emerging from conflict.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Digital preservation, a critical response to the threats facing cultural continuity, has received limited scholarly attention in Nigeria's Middle Belt, particularly in the wake of crises like the Ombatse conflict in Nasarawa State. The crisis, emblematic of wider ethno-religious tensions in Africa, led to the displacement of custodians of heritage and the endangerment of indigenous knowledge [1]. Digital preservation refers to strategies that ensure the longevity and accessibility of digital content, even amidst organizational, technological, or political upheavals [2]. The Digital Preservation Coalition [3] defines it as “all activities that are required to maintain access to digital materials beyond the limits of media failure or technological change”. These materials include both born-digital and digitized cultural content, encompassing ritual knowledge, oral histories, and communal laws. For communities like the Eggon, whose traditions are primarily transmitted orally, digital preservation becomes indispensable to intergenerational memory and resilience. This attempt was made

Abstract – Much has been written in several literatures affirming that the digital preservation of cultural heritage in contexts marked by inter-ethnic conflict is not merely an archival imperative, but an ethical and socio-political act. Communities affected by such crises frequently suffer the disappearance of both tangible heritage and the intangible frameworks of rituals, oral traditions, and collective memory that sustain cultural identity and intergenerational continuity. In light of the enduring threats posed by conflict-induced displacement and cultural fragmentation in Eggon community of Nasarawa State where over 500 lives including 84 security personnel were lost, this study was undertaken with the overarching aim of establishing conditions for the systematic digitization and safeguarding of endangered cultural heritage for present and future generations. This objective was pursued through an evaluative assessment of the institutional readiness of Libraries and cultural centres in the region, employing the Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model (DPC RAM). The study advocates the application of the six foundational elements of the DPC RAM as a baseline for initiating sustainable digital preservation strategies that are responsive to local realities and capable of supporting youth engagement, peacebuilding, and cultural revitalization. The Ombatse crisis serves as the focal point for this inquiry. Findings indicate that several structural impediments persist, including the absence of coherent preservation policies, inadequate technical infrastructure, limited digital competencies among heritage custodians, and a lack of meaningful collaboration between cultural institutions and local communities. These constraints underscore the

through the assessment of organisational capacity of cultural institutions in Nasarawa State by utilising the Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model (DPC RAM). This research proposes using the six elements of the DPC RAM as a basis for beginning the evaluation and progression towards sustainable digital preservation of cultural heritage as a tool for crisis prevention, peace building, and youth empowerment.

The Nigerian archival landscape, while rich in cultural diversity, remains underdeveloped in digital capacity. According to Ombugadu [4] the Ombatse crisis disrupted not only the sociopolitical order but also endangered sacred sites, ritual artifacts, and ancestral narratives that were previously undocumented. Much of this knowledge was at risk of being lost as elders fled and oral traditions were interrupted. In many parts of Nigeria, similar challenges persist; archival institutions either lack the infrastructure to preserve indigenous content or exclude it entirely due to colonial legacies. As highlighted by Idoko [5] obstacles to preservation in Nigeria include insufficient documentation systems, marginalization of oral knowledge, and a lack of culturally sensitive methodologies. These limitations have significant consequences for youth in affected communities, who often grow up disconnected from their cultural roots and unable to access or engage with their heritage.

These challenges also intersect with broader issues of social and political instability, as communities in Nasarawa State, Nigeria struggle not only with displacement but with a crisis of identity. The Ombatse conflict highlighted how deeply interconnected cultural identity and social cohesion are, especially in communities where heritage serves as both a source of pride and a framework for understanding the world. As cultural heritage becomes endangered by violence, displacement, and a breakdown of community structures, the importance of preserving these intangible assets grows exponentially [6]. Digital preservation, in this context, offers a way to safeguard such intangible cultural forms including rituals, languages, and traditions that are often overlooked or undervalued in traditional archival systems. The ability to digitize and store these forms of cultural expression can provide a safeguard against their erasure, while also offering opportunities for marginalized communities to reclaim their narratives.

In face of these challenges, digital preservation strategies must be inclusive, participatory, and attuned to local needs. While formal libraries and archival institutions may be absent or inaccessible, informal community-based systems of memory and knowledge transmission remain very important. These systems, however, are vulnerable in conflict zones like Nasarawa State, Nigeria and integrating the knowledge and perspectives of community members particularly the elders, youths, and local leaders into digital preservation efforts, the preservation process itself can become a tool for community resilience and empowerment especially for the youths of the community [1]. Digital technologies offer opportunities for capturing oral histories, documenting rituals, and creating archives that are owned and governed by the community. In this way, youth can become not just passive recipients of preserved knowledge but active agents of cultural regeneration and peacebuilding. Such efforts also present an opportunity for a generational dialogue thereby bridging the gap between the elders who hold traditional knowledge and the youth who are crucial to its ongoing transmission.

It is the position of this study that unless effective digital preservation frameworks and policies are developed and implemented in collaboration with local communities, the cultural losses resulting from crises like the Ombatse conflict will continue to mount. In many Nigerian institutions, preservation is constrained by inadequate policies, limited funding, and a lack of skilled personnel. However, by centering indigenous knowledge systems and adopting participatory models of digital preservation, it is possible to bridge generational divides and foster cultural continuity. The role of youth as agents of preservation and peacebuilding must be emphasized, particularly in designing digital tools and archives that are reflective of local values and accessible to those who safeguard memory not in databases, but in stories, rituals, and lived practice.

II. ABOUT THE OMBATSE CRISIS

The Ombatse crisis is rooted in the socio-cultural and political complexities of Nasarawa State, particularly among the Eggon and Alago ethnic groups. The term "Ombatse" means "time has come" in the Eggon language and refers to a spiritual movement among the Eggon people.

Founded as a form of cultural and spiritual revival, the group was primarily composed of youths who believed in protecting the values, traditions, and customs of their community. However, over time, the movement evolved in a direction that led to significant tension and violent clashes within the state. [6]

Historically, the Eggon and Alago communities have shared close relationships through intermarriages and cultural exchanges, which helped foster a sense of coexistence and mutual respect. Unfortunately, this peaceful coexistence was severely disrupted in 2012 and 2013, when longstanding land disputes escalated into violent conflict. The immediate cause of the crisis was a disagreement over the use of crown land (Padama land), which had historically been granted to the Eggon community for farming by successive paramount rulers of the Assakio Chiefdom. The tension began when the Eggon people, who had previously paid tributes for farming rights, refused to continue doing so. This act was perceived as a violation of traditional authority, prompting the paramount ruler, His Royal Highness Osula Inarigu, to restrict access to the land.

When his order was defied, and his palace envoys were attacked during an attempt to enforce it, tensions rapidly escalated. Although the government initially attempted to mediate through peaceful dialogue, hostilities erupted on June 1, 2012, when the Ombatse group reportedly launched an attack on the Alago people of Assakio, resulting in deaths, displacement, and the destruction of properties, including sacred sites like the Odu Shrine. The violence continued unchecked for several days, raising questions about the capacity of the state to intervene promptly.

Further violence occurred in September 2013, following another incident involving the interception of suspected Ombatse youths allegedly transporting weapons. The situation deteriorated after retaliatory actions by the Alago community, including the burning of a vehicle carrying the youths. In response, the Ombatse militia reportedly erected roadblocks and began abducting members of the Alago community. While local leaders attempted to de-escalate the crisis by negotiating the release of detainees and promising compensation, these peace efforts ultimately failed.

On September 13, 2013, the Ombatse group launched another wave of attacks in Obi and

Odobu, targeting Alago communities and causing widespread destruction. The violence was only brought under control after the deployment of security forces. The events of 2012 and 2013 have left a lasting impact on inter-ethnic relations in Nasarawa State and highlighted the fragility of peace in regions with unresolved historical grievances. [6]

This crisis demonstrates how cultural heritage, land rights, and youth agency intersect in complex ways. It underscores the urgent need for digital preservation initiatives that not only safeguard intangible cultural heritage but also contribute to peacebuilding and conflict prevention efforts. Understanding the crisis from a heritage perspective provides a pathway to engaging youth as agents of peace while promoting reconciliation, memory preservation, and intergenerational knowledge transfer.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

We Digital preservation plays a critical role in the modern era, especially in the context of safeguarding indigenous knowledge on cultural heritage. However, Nigeria lags behind many other nations in the digitization of such knowledge for global accessibility [5]. Scholars argue that cultural heritage institutions face significant challenges in digitizing indigenous knowledge, including inadequate funding, complex ownership protocols, digital rights management issues, loss or misplacement of digital materials, and a lack of infrastructure and skilled personnel [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]. These challenges hinder the efforts to preserve and make accessible the rich cultural heritage of Nigeria's diverse communities.

The difficulties faced by libraries and other cultural heritage institutions in Nigeria highlight the broader challenges within the country's information management systems. Libraries, museums, and archives are struggling to keep up with the demands of a technology-driven world, where digitization is increasingly seen as essential for expanding the global reach of indigenous knowledge while ensuring its preservation for future generations (UNDP 2020) [10]. The need to bridge these gaps is particularly urgent as digital preservation could play a key role in reducing socioeconomic disparities by making indigenous knowledge more accessible globally.

Despite the technological advancements that could support digital preservation, Nigeria's approach remains underdeveloped, especially when it comes to communities in conflict zones like Nasarawa State, where the Ombatse crisis has disrupted access to cultural information and heritage. These regions not only face physical displacement but also the loss of cultural continuity. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 16, which focuses on promoting peace, justice, and strong institutions, emphasizes the importance of preserving cultural heritage as a means of fostering social cohesion and conflict resolution. However, the lack of a robust framework or policy to digitize this knowledge limits its use in addressing challenges related to crisis prevention and peacebuilding [11]. This problem is exacerbated by policymakers' insufficient engagement with the critical role of digital preservation in both cultural heritage and youth empowerment. The failure to prioritize digital preservation, particularly in the aftermath of crises like the Ombatse, deprives future generations of important tools for peacebuilding and cultural sustainability.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research methodology, primarily focused on gathering insights through in-depth interviews conducted between January and March 2025 in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The fieldwork involved engaging community members, youth leaders, elders, spiritual leaders, and local officials, all of whom are key stakeholders in the preservation of cultural heritage within the Eggon community. Participants were selected based on their involvement in either the cultural practices of the community or their experience in peacebuilding efforts, ensuring a broad representation of perspectives.

Each participant was interviewed individually, ensuring that their responses were captured in a manner that reflected their personal experiences and insights. In addition to the interviews, a comprehensive desk review of relevant literature, policy documents, and previous reports on the Ombatse crisis was conducted. This review provided contextual background on the cultural dynamics of the Eggon people and the impact of the crisis on their cultural heritage.

V. CULTURAL HERITAGE PRESERVATION POLICY

The preservation of cultural heritage in Nigeria, particularly in conflict-prone regions such as Borno State, Plateau State, Kaduna State and Nasarawa State, remains largely policy deficient. While Nigeria adopted key international instruments like the UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions (2005), the practical domestication of these frameworks in national and subnational cultural policy is inconsistent [12]. Nigeria's National Cultural Policy of 1988 [13] outlines the need to safeguard traditional knowledge and promote national identity, but its implementation has largely neglected community-based institutions and oral heritage systems [14]. The Ombatse crisis revealed the deep vulnerabilities in such omissions, as sacred spaces and intangible knowledge systems were left unprotected in the wake of conflict [4]. Moreover, traditional custodians remain structurally excluded from policy-making, reinforcing epistemic marginalization and historical silencing of indigenous archives [9]. Without policies that integrate community-based preservation practices and digital innovation, heritage custodians continue to operate in a vacuum, isolated from state-sponsored frameworks of cultural sustainability.

VI. DIGITAL PRESERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE FOR CRISIS PREVENTION

In societies facing recurring interethnic crises, digital preservation plays a preemptive role in preventing violence by strengthening collective identity and community memory. The Ombatse conflict illustrated how a lack of documented cultural memory, particularly among displaced youth, can accelerate identity crises that contribute to social fragmentation [10]. In regions like Nasarawa, where oral transmission dominates and formal archival systems are weak or absent, digital preservation offers a strategy for capturing endangered rituals, languages, and histories before they are lost to conflict or displacement [15]. Scholars such as [16] emphasize that preservation must be anticipatory rather than reactive engaging communities before crisis unfolds, especially in multicultural societies where historical grievances are intergenerationally transmitted. By embedding heritage materials into digital platforms accessible to communities and researchers alike, digital preservation transforms cultural memory into a

dynamic peace infrastructure, helping to mitigate misinformation and stereotype-driven violence.

VII. DIGITAL PRESERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE FOR PEACEBUILDING

Digital preservation contributes to peacebuilding by reactivating cultural spaces and epistemologies that foster dialogue, mutual recognition, and healing in post-conflict communities. The Eggon people's use of traditional institutions such as Ombatse reflects a resilient cultural logic grounded in social cohesion and communal justice [4]. While media narratives often portray such institutions as militant, closer inspection reveals their historical roles in intergenerational education, dispute resolution, and moral guidance [17]. When these institutions are digitally preserved, they provide a counter-narrative to dominant portrayals and allow communities to reclaim agency over their histories. As Masenya note [18], community archives can function as "radical interventions" in post-conflict reconciliation, offering tools for restorative justice and cultural continuity. Digitizing rituals, oral testimonies, and community jurisprudence enables formerly marginalized groups to narrate their trauma and resilience on their own terms thus contributing to social healing and interethnic understanding.

VIII. DIGITAL PRESERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE FOR YOUTH EMPOWERMENT

Youth are often caught between the erosion of traditional knowledge systems and the inadequacy of state-supported identity frameworks. In Nasarawa State, the disruption caused by the Ombatse crisis further alienated young people from their cultural roots, as custodians fled and sacred knowledge went undocumented [10]. Digital preservation offers a pathway for youth to reconnect with heritage while gaining technical, archival, and storytelling skills that are locally grounded and globally relevant. Community-based digitization efforts, such as oral history projects and participatory digital archives, position youth not as passive consumers of heritage but as active curators and custodians [6]. This participatory approach fosters a renewed sense of belonging and responsibility, bridging generational gaps and cultivating leadership capacities rooted in cultural identity. Moreover, digital tools can be leveraged for cultural entrepreneurship enabling youth to create

digital exhibitions, cultural tourism content, and educational platforms that sustain heritage while promoting economic inclusion.

IX. DIGITAL PRESERVATION COALITION RAM MODEL

The Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model (DPC RAM) provides a structured framework for assessing and enhancing institutional digital preservation capacity. Applied in the Nigerian context, as in the case of Ramat Library, [15] the model reveals significant gaps in organizational viability, policy articulation, IT capability, and community engagement. The DPC RAM's six organizational elements Organizational Viability, Policy and Strategy, Legal Basis, IT Capability, Continuous Improvement, and Community are particularly instructive for conflict-prone settings like Nasarawa State, where institutional memory and infrastructural resilience are weak. Within the scope of this study, DPC RAM functions not only as a diagnostic tool but as a roadmap for long-term preservation planning. For example, in assessing cultural institutions affected by the Ombatse conflict, the model can guide the development of inclusive governance structures that integrate youth, elders, and cultural leaders in digital stewardship. As preservation becomes both a technical and socio-political act, tools like DPC RAM help align institutional readiness with ethical imperatives of justice, inclusion, and cultural sovereignty.

X. APPLICATION OF THE DPC RAM ORGANIZATIONAL CAPABILITIES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE OMBATSE CULTURAL HERITAGE CRISIS

Digital preservation, when rooted in community experience and aligned with structural frameworks like the Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model (DPC RAM), becomes more than an archival act it transforms into a strategic approach to social repair. The themes of crisis prevention, peacebuilding, and youth empowerment, especially in the aftermath of events like the Ombatse crisis in Nasarawa State, align across several DPC RAM organizational capabilities, rather than fitting neatly within a single category. As such, their efficacy is best understood at the intersection of three foundational dimensions of the model: Community, Organisational Viability, and Policy and Strategy. These pillars collectively enable the translation of cultural memory into tools for

conflict mitigation, intergenerational solidarity, and resilient futures.

The Community capability of DPC RAM is perhaps the most foundational for embedding cultural heritage work into crisis prevention and youth agency. Post-conflict communities like the Eggon require platforms where their voices are not only archived but empowered through participatory design, ownership, and agency in storytelling [18]. Oral traditions, sacred narratives, and memory capes disrupted by the Ombatse conflict can be revitalized through community-driven digital libraries and archives. These institutions do more than document they reconstruct shattered identities and foster local legitimacy by positioning youth as digital stewards and elders as epistemic authorities [1]. When community members are treated as collaborators rather than subjects of preservation, digital archives evolve into infrastructures of peace and intergenerational learning.

Simultaneously, Organisational Viability within the DPC RAM framework supports the sustainability of such community-based initiatives. Crisis prevention and youth empowerment depend not only on content creation but on the endurance of the systems that preserve and mediate that content. During the Ombatse crisis, cultural leadership structures and custodial systems were severely destabilized. Applying DPC RAM entails cultivating long-term organizational memory by embedding digital heritage units in local institutions such as cultural centers, universities, or even community libraries supported by consistent funding, training, and governance. This stability enables cultural heritage backup, cultural continuity and allows heritage preservation to contribute to social cohesion in the face of future conflicts. As Babagana & Kemboi [15] demonstrated in their assessment of Ramat Library, organizational fragility in Nigerian heritage institutions often results in lapses in documentation and generational handover, jeopardizing the role of archives in public memory.

The Policy and Strategy element of the model bridges the philosophical and operational aspects of cultural heritage as a peacebuilding tool. Without strategic direction and policies that articulate the role of digital heritage in civic healing and identity formation, preservation efforts risk

being ad hoc and unsustainable. Policies that frame cultural preservation as a conflict prevention mechanism can guide the ethical collection of narratives, rituals, and symbols. These strategies must also explicitly recognize youth not only as digital natives but as cultural intermediaries who can reinterpret heritage for contemporary relevance. [18] In Nasarawa, for example, digitizing Ombatse rites and ancestral stories under policy guidance can counter the stigmatization of the Eggon identity and reintegrate it into pluralistic narratives of Nigerian heritage.

DPC RAM Capability	Application to Ombatse Case
Community	Empowers local participation in digital heritage and peacebuilding.
Organisational Viability	Builds sustainable leadership and technical continuity for archives.
Policy and Strategy	Guides ethical collection and digitization of cultural heritage.
Legal Basis	Ensures cultural rights and access policies reflect community norms.
IT Capability	Facilitates low-tech digital documentation and local archival systems.
Continuous Improvement	Encourages feedback loops and iterative knowledge management.

Importantly, these three DPC RAM elements Community, Organisational Viability, and Policy and Strategy must function in synergy for digital preservation to impact peacebuilding and empowerment. For instance, a well-resourced but top-down preservation system may fail to engage youth or reflect community values, while grassroots projects without institutional viability may collapse under funding or leadership gaps. As such, the DPC RAM framework encourages a holistic perspective that combines structural strength with ethical relationality. When these components align, digital preservation efforts can shift from documentation to transformation, preserving not just content, but the cultural dynamics that generate resilience in the face of crisis.

XI. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

While this study has provided valuable insights into the potential of digital preservation as a mechanism for cultural resilience and social repair in post-conflict societies, it is not without limitations. First, the geographical scope of the study was restricted to Nasarawa State, specifically focusing on the Eggon community and the Ombatse institution. Although this provides depth and specificity, it may limit the generalizability of findings to other ethnic or conflict-affected communities in Nigeria or Africa.

Secondly, the study relied heavily on qualitative data, including oral testimonies and interviews with community members, elders, and youth leaders. While these perspectives are important in centering indigenous voices, they also introduce interpretative biases and rely on memory, which may be selective or emotionally influenced by trauma. Furthermore, logistical challenges such as security constraints, funding, and digital infrastructure gaps made it difficult to collect comprehensive digital materials or conduct live participatory digitization exercises.

Another significant limitation is the absence of robust institutional frameworks and preservation infrastructure within local cultural and archival bodies. This constrained the practical application of some Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model (DPC RAM) capabilities during the study, particularly in relation to legal compliance and IT capability. Additionally, ethical considerations regarding the documentation and potential exposure of sacred or esoteric knowledge also meant that certain cultural elements could not be digitally preserved or openly discussed.

These limitations, however, do not diminish the value of the study. Rather, they underscore the urgent need for future research and intervention to address these systemic gaps and to build resilient, community-based preservation frameworks that are both ethically sound and technologically sustainable.

XII. CONCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD

This study has demonstrated that digital preservation of cultural heritage particularly in crisis-affected and marginalized communities can serve as a potent instrument for conflict prevention, peacebuilding, economic development and youth empowerment. Through the lens of the Ombatse

crisis, we observe how the destruction of cultural memory and the dislocation of traditional custodianship can contribute to intergenerational fractures, identity crises, and social instability. Yet, digital technologies, when grounded in local participation and guided by ethical frameworks such as the DPC RAM, offer transformative opportunities to reclaim, preserve, and reinterpret heritage in ways that restore dignity and foster healing.

The way forward calls for integrated action across policy, education, and community development. Policymakers must prioritize cultural heritage in national frameworks for peace and reconstruction. Universities and cultural institutions should embed digital preservation into their curricula and service agendas. International organizations and funding bodies must support local initiatives with long-term investments in infrastructure, training, and legal protection.

Most importantly, further research is needed to explore hybrid models of preservation that combine traditional custodianship with emerging technologies such as AI, blockchain, and community-managed cloud systems. These innovations must be developed and deployed in ways that honor indigenous sovereignty, protect sacred knowledge, and support multilingual and multi-format access.

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